

Administrative Roles of Vice-Chancellors and Deans of Faculties in Nigerian Universities for Curbing Corona Virus (Covid-19) Pandemic in Nigeria: Henry Fayol's Approach

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ABSTRACT

Corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic has led to the total lockdown of the most of the human activities in various parts of the world, Nigeria inclusive. The outbreak poses serious concern to global educational systems. The World Health Organization (WHO) announced that the outbreak of corona virus has caused a public health emergency of international concern. Effective control measures are therefore, necessary to prevent the virus from further spreading, especially in this second wave of this new strain of corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic and to assist control the epidemic situation. One of the effective control measures is the sudden and unscheduled total lockdown of schools at various levels of education, not only in Nigerian but all over the world. Hence, on March 19, 2020, Nigerian government through the Federal Ministry of Education (FME), ordered the immediate closure of all schools at various levels, universities inclusive. Therefore, efforts to contain COVID-19 outbreak prompted the immediate sudden and unscheduled closure of Nigerian universities, which left all the university students out of school. It is therefore not arguable, that interference of corona virus pandemic has caused so many challenges on Nigerian university education. The University education, which the study is delimited to is the apex of all educational systems where the high manpower needs of any nation is produced for its all-round developments. Therefore, the Nigerian University students require proper attention and care. The Vice-Chancellors and Deans of the faculties who occupy administrative positions in Universities in Nigeria, need not only to teach these students but to create sound healthy school environment hospitable for teaching, learning and research. The sound healthy school environment is to prevent the spread of corona virus pandemic in the schools which is most likely to interfere with the teaching, learning and research processes in Nigerian Universities if allowed to spread. This study is designed to use Henry Fayol's approach to suggest how Vice-chancellors and Deans of the faculties should practically discharge their administrative roles in order to prevent Corona virus spread among the students and staff in Universities in Nigeria. This is expected to give an insight into healthy adaptive measures for both the students and staff in Universities in Nigeria. Finally, the following suggestions were made, which include: the various governing councils of Universities in Nigeria in collaboration with the Federal and state governments should provide preventive kits and other related health facilities in Universities to prevent the future spread of corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic in universities, provide infrastructures to make lecture halls' or classrooms' physical distancing possible, periodic fumigating of universities, wearing of nose and mouth masks, use of hand sanitizers, services of healthcare workers and creation of isolation centers in case of any health crises among others.

Keywords: Corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic, Vice-Chancellors, Dean of Faculties, University Education, Henry Fayol's Approach.

Introduction

Coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak has created educational disruptions, and international health concerns that proved very difficult to manage by national and global health systems. Of a truth, no nation or race across the world is immune from the coronavirus pandemic and all the countries of the world seem overwhelmed by the speed of the spread and the devastating effects of the first and second waves of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. In other words, coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has no boundaries or limitations and the effects are tremendous. It has drastically changed the lifestyles of the entire world, Nigeria inclusive, with trillions of people being forced to stay at home to observe self-isolations, international and interstate movements banned. Its new wave with the new variant of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic is tremendously devastating many countries of the world such as America, Russia, India and south African.

According to Edeh, Nwafor, Obafemi, Sen, Atonye, Sharma and Alsayed (2020), the outbreak of corona virus (COVID-19) pandemic affected every aspects of human activities worldwide, ranging from education, research, transportation, worship, sports, social gathering/interactions, entertainment, economy, politics and businesses. Of a truth, the entire world was in a very great distress, Nigeria inclusive. As a result of coronavirus (COVID-19) threats, it is imperative therefore to note that the reality of the situation was challenging to bear, and education industry remains one of the worst-hit by coronavirus (COVID-19) outburst. Infection control mechanisms are therefore necessary to prevent the coronavirus (COVID 19) Pandemic from further spreading. One of the control mechanisms is the total lockdown of schools at various levels globally. According to Adelakun (2020) on March, 19, 2020, Nigerian government through Federal Ministry of Education ordered the closure of all schools at various levels, universities inclusive. The total lockdown of universities by the Federal government of Nigeria and the state governments due to coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic outbreak has hindered teaching, learning and research which prompted sit at home for both lecturers and students as well as non-academic staff of the universities in Nigeria.

Recently, the Federal Government of Nigeria through the Federal Ministry of Education, after due consultations with relevant stakeholders, including State Governors, Commissioners of Education, Proprietors, and Heads of Institutions, Staff Unions and Students, announced that the school's resumption date of 18th January, 2021 still stands. The Federal Government of Nigeria through the Federal Ministry of Education, went further to state that parents and respective institutions, universities inclusive, must ensure full compliance with COVID-19 protocols which include:

1. Compulsory wearing of facemasks by all students, teachers and workers in all schools
2. Temperature checks and hand washing facilities at strategic locations in all schools.
3. Ensuring constant supply of water and sanitizers
4. Enforcement of maintenance of social distancing and suspension of large gathering such as assembly and visiting days.

The news that schools will reopen on 18th day of January 2021 was received by parents and guardians of students in universities with mixed feelings. According to Nsude and Otegbulu (2020), it is not arguable that it will be good for students to return back to school after the long stay at home due to coronavirus (COVID -19) pandemic. They went further to state that the parents and guardians of Secondary Education Students are fully aware that if precautionary mechanisms are not put in place in schools, the spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic will be so overwhelming. In other words, Nsude et al (2020) stated that if proper health care is not taken, there may be an outrageous increase in spread rate of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in schools, especially secondary schools. This by extension, means that if precautionary measures are not put in place in Nigerian Universities as schools reopens Monday, 18th January 2021, the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic will be so overwhelming and academic activities will be adversely affected. When the university education of a country is negatively affected, the country will be in trouble, since university is the place where the higher manpower needs of a nation is produced. Therefore, the chunk of the responsibility rests on both the vice chancellors and Deans of faculties in Nigerian universities, both State, Private and Federal. It is against this background that administrators and managers of education institutions, university education in particular, requires to take proactive measures to curb possible spread of this deadly pandemic among students, academic and nonacademic staff of the universities. University Vice Chancellors and Deans of faculties, therefore ought to strategically discharge their roles as academic and administrative heads in the universities. This study therefore, examines the administrative roles of vice chancellors and Deans of faculties in Nigerian universities in the bid to prevent coronavirus (COVID-19) spread in universities in Nigeria: Henry Fayol's approach. It will equally give an insight to school administrators and managers on adaptable health preventive measures to prevent the outbreak of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic while discharging their core administrative and managerial functions in the schools. Hence, the focus of this paper is therefore to proffer health adaptive measures for healthy schools' environment to prevent coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic outbreak among staff and students in Nigerian universities.

Overview of Coronavirus (COVID -19) Pandemic

Odunayo (2020) in Nsude and Otegbulu (2020) noted that coronavirus pandemic is contagious disease that originated in WUHAN, China in 2019. It is a mysterious health crisis that largely spread via droplet in the air. According to Boland, Kulifeld, Tarasama, Johnson, Ruzek and Liu (2020), these are typically expelled when an infected person coughs or sneezes. According to them, the coronavirus is transmitted through direct contact with respiratory droplets of an infected person or through touching surfaces contaminated with the virus and touching faces such as eyes, nose and mouth. Coronavirus has been estimated to have an incubation period of 14 days. According to World Health Organization (WHO 2020), there have been various known coronavirus that cause illness ranging from common cold to more severe diseases. According to UNICEF, (2020), the COVID-19 virus may survive on surfaces for several hours but simple disinfectants can kill it. UNICEF (2020) went further to state that older, and people with chronic medical conditions, such as diabetes and heart diseases, appear to be more at risk of developing severe symptoms and being easily infected.

Currently there is vaccine for coronavirus but it has not been generally accepted as a permanent cure for coronavirus without severe effects. Hence, there are arguments on whether to use coronavirus vaccine for the cure of coronavirus or not especially in African countries. However, according to New scientists (2020), the following measures should be taken to curb, the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic:

1. Staying at home when sick
2. washing hands often with soap and water for about 20 seconds
3. Frequently cleaning of touched surfaces and objects
4. Cover mouth and nose with flexed elbow or tissue when coughing or sneezing. Dispose of tissue immediately. According to Wang and Liu (2020), the best approach to COVID-19 is to control the source of infection; use infection prevention and control measures to lower the risk of transmission, and provide early diagnosis, isolation and supportive care for affected patients.

Furthermore, Federal Government of Nigeria has deployed various preventive and management mechanism to reduce the spread of the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. Such mechanisms include: closure of schools, nationwide lockdown, bans of public gatherings (churches, markets, banks, restaurants, wedding, meetings, social events, conferences, seminars and workshops), curfew, mandatory sit at home and restrictions on travels, among others, all in the bid to reduce coronavirus (COVID-19) spread. However, despite the efforts made by the federal government and various state governments, to curb the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, the rising trend of the infection in the country continues unabated. Odunayo (2020) noted that if more intervention is not put in place in Nigeria to curb the spread of coronavirus, as schools are to reopen on 18th Jan 2021, education industry might be adversely affected by the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic.

Igbokwe, Okeke –James, Ndidiamaka, Akudo and Anyanwu (2020) noted that many administrative heads in Nigerian universities fail to realize that if proper care is not taken, there will be an outrageous increase in spread rate of coronavirus in Nigerian universities, where higher manpower needs of the nation is produced. To this effect, the administrators and managers of education institutions, university education in particular, requires to take proactive measures to curb possible outbreak and spread of this deadly pandemic among students and staff. Vice Chancellors and Deans of faculties in Nigerian universities (private, state and federal) therefore, ought to strategically discharge their roles as academic and administrative heads in the school. Hence, this paper is out to proffer healthy adaptive mechanisms for healthy school environment to reduce coronavirus outburst among students and staff in Nigerian Universities.

Effect of coronavirus school closure

According to Edeh, Nwafor, Obafemi, Sen, Atonye, Sharma and Alsayed (2020) cited in Nsude and Otegbulu (2020), school closure means the closing down of schools as a result of the pandemic, emergencies, labour strikes, disasters or deliberate efforts to reposition a school or curb crimes in a given campus or environment. Nsude and Otegbulu (2020) noted that school closures are not only for emergencies or pandemic but a prudent deliberate way of addressing some identified gaps in a given school or environment. According to them, in Nigeria, school authorities often shutdown schools to address security issues such as cultism, kidnapping Boko haram activities, terrorism or violent protest on the campus. According to Nsude and Otegbulu (2020), the emergence of coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic and its increasing incidence in all states of Nigeria, Enugu state inclusive, remains one of the worst global pandemics for decades. They went further to stress that it has created severe pressure on Enugu State Educational institutions resulting into academic downturn in Enugu state educational system. Consequently, according to them, led to serious disruptions in academic activities as well as in career plans in Enugu State. According to Lindzon (2020) in Nsude et al (2020). School closure have made negative impact on students, teachers, and families. According to

him, school closures in response to coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic have shed light on various social and economic issues. He went further to state that the impact was more severe for disadvantaged children and their families, causing interrupted learning, compromised nutrition, childcare problems and consequent economic cost to families who could not work. Madeline (2020) cited in Nsude and Otegbulu (2020) agreed with Lindzon (2020), when he noted that school closures due to coronavirus has posed new problems like how to make the transition to online and at home learning and how to cater for those who rely on school for food and housing security. Protracted school closures according to Edeh et al (2020) may result to increase rate of dropouts due to loss of interest and lack of resources to continue schooling. UNICEF (2020) agreed with Edeh et al (2020) when they stated that a long period of disengagement from school can result in a further increase of dropout rate, as Nigeria contributes approximately 20% of the global out of school population. According to Eseyim and Akintunde (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic is revolutionizing digital and online education globally but children in rural and disadvantaged communities in Nigeria, are left behind as they lack fund and learning materials needed to adapt or transit to the new methods. According to UNESCO (2020b) cited in Edeh et al (2020), some of the harmful effects of school closures for coronavirus are as follows:

1. **Interrupted learning:** School provides essential learning and when they are closed, students are deprived of opportunities for growth and development
2. **Nutrition:** Many youngsters on free or discounted meals provided at schools for food and health nutrition. This is compromised as a result of school closures for coronavirus.
3. **Unequal Access to digital learning portals:** Lack of access to technology or good internet connectivity for continued learning during school closures.
4. **Increased pressure on schools and school system that remains open:** localized school closures place burdens on school as parents tend to redirect their children to open schools.
5. **School isolation:** Considering the fact that educational institutions are hubs for social activity and human interactions, school closures can deprive youths and children of some social communications and socializations that are essential to learning, development and creativity.

Furthermore, Edeh et al (2020) reported that research activities were negatively affected because school closures and lockdowns limit researcher's ability to conduct researches particularly in situations whereby face to face interactions with students and teachers are required or access to school facilities or research laboratories were denied. They went further to stress that school driven innovations and research are also affected during school closures, especially at university level.

University Education

According to Amadi (2014), university is the apex of all the tertiary institutions. According to him, it is expected to make optimum contribution to national development by intensifying and diversifying its programs for the development of high-level manpower needs of national requirements, making professional course content to reflect on national requirement. It is a citadel of learning and it is regarded as the highest providing level of education in Nigeria and other countries of the world. It is imperative to know that students of these ivory towers are required to acquire skills, knowledge and information that make the society to be preserved and enriched as a result of their level of input into the system. According to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013), the national policy on education states that university education is education for the production of high-level manpower needs of the society. Therefore, the importance of university education made the federal government of Nigeria to state that university education shall make optimum contributions to national development by:

- a. Intensifying and diversifying its programs for the development of high-level manpower within the content of the needs of the nation.
- b. Making professional course contents reflect our national requirements.
- c. Making all students part of a general program of all-round improvement in university education, to offer general study courses such as history of ideas, philosophy of knowledge, nationalism, and information technology and;
- d. Making entrepreneurial skills acquisition a requirement for all Nigerian Universities.

Furthermore, according to National policy on Education (2013),

- a. University research shall be relevant to the nation's development goals. In view of this, particular attention shall be paid to research and promotion of indigenous knowledge in Nigeria. In this regard, universities shall be encouraged to collaborate with government, industries and the global community in the conduct of research and disseminate the results.

- b. University teaching shall seek to inculcate community spirit in the students through projects and action researches.
- c. Technologically-based professional courses in the universities shall include, as components, exposure to relevant future working environment.
- d. It is imperative that teachers in professional fields have relevant industrial and professional experience and exposure
- e. Sizeable proportion of expenditure on university education shall be devoted to science.
- f. Not less than 60% of places shall be allocated to science and science-oriented courses in the conventional universities of Technology and Agriculture.

From the foregoing, the goals and objectives of university education, make it tremendously clear that the future of any nation does not only depends on the quality of education it provides for its citizens at this level but also on the health conditions of the students and staff at this apex level of education. This is because healthy environment is vital to teaching, learning and research especially in this era of new variation of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic that is devastating almost all countries of the world, African countries inclusive. Proactive measures must be taken by the university authorities in order to annihilate the outburst and spread of the new strain of the coronavirus (COVID-19) that is devastating many countries of the world, our universities having survived the first outbreak that led to the first lockdown of all activities in the nation, school closures, inclusive.

Although there are other key stake holders in the business of university education, vice-chancellors and deans of the faculties are the major determinants of its products, since both directs the teaching and learning process in the universities through the heads of various departments and other lecturers. Vice-chancellors are the most senior lecturers, leaders and administrators in university education. According to Igbokwe, Okeleke, Akudo and Anyanwu (2020) cited in Nsude and Otegbulu (2020) as administrators they oversee educational programs and provide a guide for effective daily administration of the schools. Furthermore, Jaiyoba (2003) in Nsude (2015), a principal is a secondary school administrator who has to organize and direct the affairs of the school in such a way to achieve its goals and objectives. He went further to stress that he is the person responsible for coordinating the activities of the school, using the resources at his disposal in such a way that school objectives are achieved. On the same vein, vice-chancellors are the administrators of university education and as administrators, they oversee, direct, coordinate and supervise all the activities of the universities in such a manner that the goals and objectives of the universities are achieved. Therefore, university vice-chancellors are essentially organizers and coordinators, who have to work with deans of the faculties, heads of departments and other lecturers, as a team in order to achieve the desired goals and objectives of the schools. According to Craige (2018), the role of educational administrators includes: setting the institution's tone, setting policy that staff and students will abide by. It is imperative to know that the deans of the faculties, heads of departments and other lecturers are group of people charged with the responsibility of teaching, training, encouraging and inspiring the students to learn. More strongly, the deans of faculties, heads of departments and other lecturers are not just charged with the responsibility to impart knowledge and skills on students but also to guide, teach, motivate and look after them.

Consequently, how the students receive what they do in the lecture halls or classrooms and the relationship they are able to establish with other aspects of life, depends on how the deans of faculties, head of departments and other lecturers, present and coordinate teaching-learning process. According to Craige (2018), the roles of educational administrators include: setting the institution's tone, setting policy that staff and students will abide by. Hence vice-chancellors and deans of the faculties are the administrators in the universities, who set the tones or climates of the universities as well as setting the policy both the staff and students will abide by, especially in this era of new variation of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic that is already devastating many countries of the world. Henry Fayol (1845-1925) outlined five administrative management functions, which are as follows: planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling. In this study, the researchers, used administrative management functions outlined by Henry Fayol to proffer preventive health measures in coronavirus, especially in this era of new variation of coronavirus (COVID-19) and post coronavirus pandemic in universities in Nigeria.

Vice chancellors' Application of Henry Fayol's Administrative Functions in Nigerian Universities

The most practical measures, vice chancellors can apply Henry Fayol's administrative functions (Planning, organizing, directing, coordinating and controlling) in preventing coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in both public and private universities in Nigeria, especially now the new strain of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic is tremendously causing serious health crises in many countries of the world, African inclusive, are as follows:

1. **Application of planning in the universities:** Planning is a process used to identify and select appropriate goals and course of action to achieve the goals (Jones, George and Hill, 2015). According to Fayol, planning defines the organizational objectives which sets the stage for the other functions of a manager's job.

According to Koontz (1980) cited in Edeokwor (2018), planning is deciding in advance what to do, how to do it, when to do it, where to do it, who is to do it and even why it should be done. According to Okwori, cited in Nwogbo (2014), planning is an intelligent process of preparing or arranging a set of decisions for future action directed at achieving goals, and objectives by the best possible means or methods. Application of this function in the Nigerian universities requires that the vice-chancellors should design the best possible mechanisms of annihilating coronavirus (COVID-19) outbreak and spread in Nigeria Universities. The preventive mechanism should involve the following:

- i. **Identify and assigning the hygiene facility's Needs:** There is a great need for proper identification of areas of poor hygiene facilities in the universities, faculty by faculty, department by department and in all offices. The Vice –Chancellors should not only identify the areas of poor hygiene facilities in the universities but should plan ways of assigning these identified duties to his/her subordinates (Deans of various faculties) so as to enhance the hygiene situations in the universities. It is imperative, according to Nsude and Otegbulu (2020) for the principals to identify and assign duties to things like portable drinking water, rest rooms, isolation centers, disinfectants detergents, hand sanitizers, wash hand basins, nose and mouth masks, fumigating school compound, health care services and facilities. On the same vein, the vice –chancellors will not only identify and assign these areas but will plan with the help of the Deans of the faculties, the best possible ways to achieve success in the fight against the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) Pandemic in Nigeria universities. For proper guidance and management and for better results too, the vice chancellors should employ the services of universities' medical centers.
 - ii. **Deploying of Resources Both Human and Materials:** The vice chancellors should identify and assign duties to heads of departments through the deans of the faculties, even in sourcing information on health matters, as well as drawing up budget by making survey from reliable sources so as to make purchases and supply of the hygiene facilities.
 - iii. **Involvement of the Education Stakeholders:** The vice-chancellors of Nigerian universities should wisely and strategically involve other education stakeholders in the universities through the Deans of faculties on the issue of healthcare facilities and treatment. This is because participatory leadership, involving heads of various departments and other lecturers through Deans of the faculties, as well as directors and non-academic staff is of great important to achieving health goal.
2. **Application of organizing in the universities:** Organizing implies putting together both human and material resources in such a manner, that output could be possible and successful, effective and efficient. According to Jones, George, Hill and Longton (2016), organizing is a process used to establish a structure of working relationships that allow organizational members to work together to achieve organizational goals. They went further to stress that organizing involves grouping people into departments according to the kinds of job-specific tasks they perform. In the words of Abulkareem and Oduwayo (2017), organizing involves arranging activities and resources for effective classroom behavior and performance. Fayol believed that an organization should be structured to provide unity of direction, clearly defined responsibilities, spur initiative and encourage responsibility, harmonize activities and coordinate efforts as well as ensuring control without any rigid regulation, red tape and paper control. The vice-chancellors in Nigerian universities achieve this through assigning duties to university staff such as posting coronavirus (COVID-19) protocols rules and school hygiene rule at strategic places in the school, especially at the school gate and entrances of every faculties and offices. They can also form special task force on COVID-19, that will be saddled with the responsibility to ensure compliance to coronavirus (COVID-19) protocols as well as ensuring that adherence to the school hygiene COVID -19 protocols as a guarantee for gaining entrance to school premises and creating a special squad in case of health emergency need. Therefore, to prevent the outburst and spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian universities, the vice-chancellors should lay out the lines of authority and responsibility between different individuals and groups and they decide how best to organize the hygiene facilities such as hand sanitizers, nose and mouth masks, water detergents, disinfectants, wash hand basins and buckets and fumigating of school premises and offices in order to annihilate the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) in universities.
 3. **Application of directing in the universities:** Fayol in Jumare (2018) maintained that directing is to ensure compliance with the acceptable rules and regulations and that heads of organizations must lead by example. According to him, this leading by example will motivate workers to put more efforts and make sure that work is done according to schedule. Directing therefore is to ensure that staff performs their duties and students exhibit expected hygiene behaviors in the school in accordance with the acceptable rules and regulations of the school. Vice chancellors' application of this administrative function in

preventing the spread of COVID-19 in universities is to ensure that academic staff and other supportive staff perform their duties and students as well as visitors exhibit the expected hygiene behaviors in the schools. The vice-chancellors should do this, by the provision of hygiene facilities in every classroom, libraries, offices, playgrounds, cafeterias, adequate supervision and monitoring to ensure that none of the hygiene facilities or behaviors is ignored by the academic staff, supportive staff, students and visitors or any other person(s) who has to do anything within university community.

4. **Application of controlling in the universities:** In the words of Onyedjeji (2017) cited in Igbokwe, Okeke – James, Ndidiamaka, Akudo and Anyanwu (2020), controlling is function that is targeted at eliminating all forms of waste (time, materials and funds) so as to meet the set standard. According to Nwangwu, Otegbulu and Eze (2017), control consists of verifying whether everything appears in conformity with plan adopted, the instruction issued and the established principles. According to Fayol in Nwangwu et al (2017) the main aim of control is to identify weaknesses or errors in order to control and forestall their recurrence. In controlling according to Jones, George, Hill and Longton (2018), managers evaluate how well an organization is achieving its goals and act to maintain or improve performance. In preventing the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian universities, the vice-chancellors should set up a monitoring mechanism to monitor the performance of individuals, faculties, department, offices, school business activities and universities as a whole to see whether they are meeting absolute compliance to the school hygiene COVID-19 safety protocols in order to annihilate possible out break and spread of coronavirus (COVID -19) pandemic in the schools. Practically, the vice –chancellors should ensure proper health records and purchases inventory through the health care workers and bursar respectively so as to ensure proper accountability. Furthermore, they should ensure adequate control and provision for portable water, washing soap, preferably liquid soap, hand sanitizers, nose and mouth masks for staff, students and any other person(s) who has any activity to perform within university communities.
5. **Application of coordinating in the universities:** By coordination, Fayol in Nwangwu, Otegbulu and Eze (2017), meant to harmonize all the activities of the organization in order to facilitate its working as well as its success.

According to Jumare (2018), coordinating refers to efforts made by heads of organization towards making sure that activities, facilities and programs are put at the right place and at right time. Coordination also could be seen as ensuring that every faculties, departments and segments perform their duties without or less challenges. In respect to coronavirus (COVID -19) pandemic, coordinating is steering the activities of all stakeholders' efforts geared towards curbing COVID-19 spread in the school. The vice chancellors will effectively achieve these functions by: regular meetings with universities' governing councils, Deans of the faculties, and heads of supportive staff for a good flow of information, regularly fumigating the university environment, ensuring proper disposal of waste preferably via incineration, creating steady coronavirus (COVID-19) awareness in the university using manual and electronic devices.

Deans of Faculties Application of Henry Fayol's Administrative Functions

Deans of faculties in universities in Nigeria are the faculties administrative heads or managers and as such perform administrative functions in the faculties. They administer administrative functions in order to enhance effective teaching and learning process. In doing this, he/she through the heads of various departments in the faculty, creates conducive atmosphere hospitable not only for teaching and learning, but for good health environment, especially in this era of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. The most practical mechanisms, the deans of the faculties in universities in Nigeria both federal, State and private can adopt Henry Fayol's administrative functions (planning, organizing, director coordinating and controlling) in preventing coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic outburst in both federal, state and private Universities in Nigeria are as follows:

1. **Application of Planning in Universities:** Planning is a process used to identify and select appropriate and attainable goals and courses of action to achieve the predetermine goals. In planning there are three necessary steps that are involved:
 - I. Deciding which goals to pursue
 - II. Deciding what courses of action to adopt to achieve the set goals
 - III. Deciding how to allocate available resources to achieve the set goals.

Planning fundamentally according to chikeleze (2017) involves the selection of organizational objectives as well as determining ways of attaining them through consciously determined courses of action. In applying this administrative function in universities in Nigeria, the deans of faculties will not only set specific, measurable, achievable and realistic goals in collaboration with the heads of the departments but will determine courses of action to achieve the goals using available resources. Hence in preventing the

outburst and spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian universities deans of faculties in collaboration with the heads of various departments, lecturers, students and other supportive staff will not only set goals on how to prevent the COVID-19 pandemic spread, but courses of action to stop the spread using available resources. They achieve this by: decongesting crowded lecture halls or classrooms in order to maintain social and physical distancing maximally, making adequate provision of hygiene facilities (toiletries, disinfectants, sanitizers, water, detergents, wash hand basins and buckets) in all the lecture halls or classrooms. They will set joint action committee comprising of course representatives, assistant course representatives, lecturers and supportive staff that will be saddled with responsibility of ensuring absolute or zero compliance to all the schools' COVID-19 safety protocols.

2. **Application of Organizing in The Universities:** Organizing is a process used to establish a structure of working relationship that allow organizational members to work together in order to achieve organizational goals. Fayol in Nwangwu, Otegbulu and Eze (2017) sees organizing as managers job that involves providing organization with all the things it needs to realize its objectives. The deans of faculties will achieve this function in the fight against the spread of COVID-19 pandemic in universities by creating a structure of working relationships among the heads of departments, other lecturers, students and supportive staff, mapping out lecture hall hygiene rules and penalty for defaulters, lecturers strategically sandwiching coronavirus (COVID-19) awareness in the course of their lecturing and giving assignments and quiz. Furthermore, they will equally achieve this function by setting a special task force on prevention of COVID-19 pandemic spread saddled with that responsibilities of decongesting crowded lecture halls so the social and physical distancing are maximally maintained as well as ensuring total compliance to the school's hygiene COVID-19 safety protocols.
3. **Application of Directing in The Universities:** In the administrative function of directing, it is the human resources that are being directed to mobilize and make prudent use of other resources in accordance with the established rules and regulations to achieve organizational goals and objectives. In directing, according to Jones, George, Hill and Langton (2018), managers articulate a clear vision for organization members so that they understand the part they play and how to play it in achieving organizational goals and objectives. The deans of the faculties will achieve this function by prudently directing the heads of the departments, other lecturers, students and supportive staff to make good use of available hygiene facilities (sanitizers, liquid soaps, water, school isolation centers, healthcare services, disinfectant, fumigating chemicals) in the fight against the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian universities. The deans of faculties will achieve this effectively by ensuring adequate supervision through exemplary healthy living and behavior for students and other staff to emulate as well as ensuring total compliance to the COVID-19 safety protocols in the faculties.
4. **Application of Controlling in The Universities:** In controlling, administrative organizational heads monitor the performance of individuals, departments and organization as a whole to ascertain whether they are meeting desired performance standards. If standards are not being met, administrative heads take appropriate and adequate action to improve performance. According to Jones et al (2018), organization administrative head, evaluates how well an organization is achieving its goals and objectives and take appropriate action to maintain or improve performance. According to them, individuals working in groups have also the responsibility of controlling, that is making sure the group achieves its goals and actions. In order to exercise control in the fight against the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, in universities in Nigeria, deans of the faculties must decide what he/she wants to achieve in the fight, and then they must design information and control system that will provide data they need to assess performance. These mechanisms, when effectively done, will provide feedback to the deans of faculties and the deans of faculties will also provide feedback to the heads of departments, other lecturers, students and supportive staff of the faculties. The feedback is vital in curbing the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian Universities, since it provides useful information on the environmental health conditions of the school. Also, the heads of departments under the control and supervision of the deans of the faculties should ensure adequate classroom hygiene evaluation such as ensuring decongestion of crowded classroom so as to maintain social and physical distancing, washing of hands before entering the lecture halls or classrooms and mandatory use of nose and mouth mask as criterion for entrance to lecture halls or classrooms. Furthermore, the controlling function in this fight against the spread of COVID-19 pandemic in Nigerian Universities, enables the deans of faculties to evaluate how well, they themselves are performing the other three functions of management-planning, organizing and directing in this era of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic. Consequently, this will lead them to take corrective measures or action,

where necessary, so to achieve effectiveness and efficiency in the fight against the spread of COVID-19 pandemic in Nigerian Universities

5. **Application Of Coordinating In The Universities:** According to Jumare (2018) , coordinating refers to efforts made by heads of organization towards making sure that activities, facilities and programmers are put at the right place and at the right time. It is the process of ensuring that the performance in an organization takes place in accordance with planned performance. According to Fayol in Nwangwu et al (2017), coordinating means to harmonize all the activities of an organization in order to facilitate its working as well as its success. Fayol therefore advised to achieve effective coordination, there should be regular meetings with the administrative heads in order to ensure good flow of information which is central to organizational success. For easy administration of the faculties in Nigerian universities, in terms of curbing the spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in schools, among others, the deans of faculties must ensure proper classroom coordination through the heads of various departments, ensuring that students maintain school hygiene behaviors such as: cover nose and mouth when sneezing, avoidance of close or body contact with friends, fellow students and well-wishers and avoiding wasting available hygiene facilities provided in the faculties by the university authority.

Conclusion

The emergency of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has adversely affected education of countries, all over the world, Nigeria inclusive. The outburst of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic has not only shaken Nigerian educational system off its strengths, effectiveness and efficiency but has caused noticeable academic downturn in all levels of education system of Nigerian, university education system inclusive. It has not only caused great harm to all levels of education industry in Nigerian but has put severe pressure on all levels of Nigerian educational industry especially university education industry where the high manpower needs of the nation is produced. With the recent new strain of coronavirus outbreak that is currently rampaging almost all countries of the world, African countries inclusive, swift and deceive actions have to be taken to mitigate the spread in the universities in Nigerian. Therefore, healthy training and habits are among the essential prerequisite for curbing coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian universities especially now the new strain of coronavirus which has been causing great harm in many countries of the world. Currently this new strain of coronavirus has caused the second total lockdown of schools in many countries of the world with its consequent effects on education system, particularly university education. University education is the educational system where the higher manpower needs of a nation are produced. It also determined the quality and quantity of imputes from secondary education to be admitted for the production of the higher manpower needs of the nation. This explains why effective measures must be put in place by the university vice-chancellors and deans of faculties as well as heads of various departments, other lecturers, students and supportive staff to curb the possible spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Nigerian universities especially in this new wave of this new strain of coronavirus (COVID-19).

Suggestions

Based on the above administrative management functions, the following suggestions were made.

1. With the emergency of new strain of coronavirus (COVID-19) in some countries of the world, African countries inclusive, although not yet so pronounced as in other developed countries of the world, futuristic plan has to be made by the government and concerned educational personnel to ensure that the future of university education is secured and also in case of another similar global health crises.
2. The governing councils of universities in Nigeria, as well as federal and state governments should make provision for preventive kits in universities and other related health facilities to curb the future spread of coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in our universities
3. The future of our country's university education is on the hands of every one of us and we can never allow it to be soiled with the interference of coronavirus; or any other future health crises. Private sectors and concerned individuals should come in, to rescue it from impending doom which may spring up as a result of the emergery outbreak of the new strain of coronavirus that has already been devastating some countries of the world. They can do this by providing health facilities and other necessary infrastructures to make classroom physical distancing possible.
4. Vice-chancellors in Nigerian universities should ensure acquiring adequate and relevant hygiene facilities where they are not sufficient
5. Deans of faculties, heads of departments and other lecturers should instill hygiene consciousness and information into students.

6. The students, lecturers and supportive staff should always endeavor to maintain healthy hygiene habits and behaviors all the time.
7. The vice-chancellors and deans of the faculties should ensure strict adherence to the school hygiene rules (such as wearing of nose and mouth mask always, regular washing of hands with soap, water and sanitizers as well as Maintaining social and physical distancing as a guarantee not only for gaining entrance into the school premises but into the lecture halls or classrooms.
8. The class representatives in collaboration with their assistants, should ensure that class members exhibit all the expected hygiene behaviors and that none of the hygiene facilities or behaviors in the lecture halls or classrooms is ignored by the students.
9. The vice-chancellors and deans of faculties should regularly fumigate school environment, offices and lecture halls. They should also ensure regular and proper disposal of waste preferably through incineration.
10. The vice-chancellors and deans of the faculties should create steady COVID-19 awareness in universities in Nigerian, using manuals, or hand bills, healthcare workers and electronic devices such as computers, projectors, power points and television.
11. Finally, Nigerian government, both federal and state, as well as private university owners should encourage e-learning in all the universities in Nigeria.

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